

Abstract

Ethical implications of the use of technology in the training and professional practice of psychology

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Abstract: The training process in psychology requires addressing three dimensions: theoretical training, training in practice and personal training (Cruz, 2009; Landa-Durán Peñalosa, 2009). Until now, the theoretical dimension is carried out with the help of various technological tools such as video calls, audiovisual material, educational apps or free access tools to be used on any electronic device; although in many cases the teaching practice is carried out only with tools mastered by the teacher (Carlos-Guzmán et al, 2021), but it would be necessary to investigate how the practical and personal dimension mediated by technology unfolds. According to Carolina Santillán (2021), the public university has a moral responsibility to pay attention to the mental health conditions of its students, coupled with the urgency of providing academics with tools to intervene in situations that could alter mental health of the students. Faced with the postponement of face-to-face meetings, the reduction in classroom capacity and the urgent need for on-site training typical of a science such as psychology, a transcendent problem emerges for us to analyze and act accordingly. For these reasons, advances of a doctoral investigation are made known where the training process in psychology is analyzed in various universities in Mexico and Latin America mainly, with the purpose of highlighting its transformation in the face of the challenges of today's society such as the implementation of technology in education and professional practice, the replacement of face-to-face with virtuality and the creation of new educational scenarios that meet the training demand in each case. The research recovers different documented experiences regarding professional training, giving an account of the essential pedagogical elements to guarantee said process, thus safeguarding scientific rigor and promoting the ethics that mental health care demands (Urdiales et. al, 2021).

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